

1 **CBR3 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.**

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6 Glioblastoma is difficult to treat and patients are often provided poor prognosis (1), indicating a
7 requirement for therapeutic target identification and drug development. Differentially expressed genes
8 represent by definition among the most promising targets for the development of novel chemotherapies (2,
9 3). We predict therapeutic index is intrinsically linked to differential expression which can be
10 comprehensively and blindly determined using whole transcriptome data, further limiting toxicity by
11 design (4). We mined published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify
12 differentially expressed gene products in glioblastoma by performing whole transcriptome gene expression
13 profiling. We found that the gene encoding the carbonyl reductase 3, CBR3, was among those whose
14 expression was most different in human glioblastoma tumors when comparing total transcription between
15 tumor and normal brain tissue. CBR3 expression levels were significantly increased in glioblastoma
16 tumors as compared to the non-transformed brain. CBR3 function at the systems level was assessed by
17 studying whole transcriptome transcriptional co-regulation in the transformed brain. CBR3 is a target of
18 interest for the treatment of glioblastoma, as part of a rationally designed chemotherapeutic regimen that
19 utilizes gene expression data from patient tumors and healthy non-transformed tissues to maximize
20 efficacy and safety and minimize toxicity.

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26 Keywords: CBR3, carbonyl reductase 3, glioblastoma, systems biology of glioblastoma, targeted
27 therapeutics in glioblastoma.

Brain cancer encompasses a spectrum of solid tumors that affect the brain in children and adults including medulloblastoma, neuroblastoma, and glioblastoma (7). Rational development of targeted therapeutics to treat patients with glioblastoma can be supported by an enhanced understanding of fundamental transcriptional differences that define the glioblastoma tumor. To discover genes associated with glioblastoma in humans in an unbiased fashion and at the systems level, we compared total transcription in the normal brain and in the glioblastoma tumor using published and public human glioblastoma microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) to identify a molecular signature or fingerprint of glioblastoma, among the most lethal and difficult to treat solid tumors affecting adults. We describe here identification of a potential therapeutic target in glioblastoma based on quantitative whole transcriptome methods.

Methods

We utilized microarray datasets GSE116520 (5) and GSE184643 (6) for this differential gene expression analysis of the brain cancer glioblastoma in humans using R-based computational methods (GEO2R). GSE116520 was generated using Illumina HumanHT-12 V4.0 expression beadchip technology; for this analysis, we used $n=8$ control brain tissue and $n=17$ glioblastoma tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL10558. GSE184643 was generated using Illumina NovaSeq 6000 (Homo sapiens) technology; for this analysis, we used $n=3$ control brain tissue and $n=3$ glioblastoma tumors, and the analysis was performed using platform GPL24676. All tumors utilized for differential gene expression analysis here were of the adenocarcinoma type. The Benjamini and Hochberg method of p-value adjustment was used for ranking of differential expression but raw p-values were used to assess statistical significance of global differential expression. Log-transformation of data was auto-detected, and the NCBI generated category of platform annotation was used. SEEK was utilized for transcriptional co-regulation studies (8).

Results

We harnessed the power of whole transcriptome technologies and cross-laboratory validation (5, 6) to discover in an unbiased fashion and at the transcriptome level the most distinguishing gene expression features of the human brain cancer glioblastoma.

CBR3 is differentially expressed in glioblastoma.

1. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with glioblastoma

$n=8$ normal brain tissues (human)

$n=17$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

ID	<i>p</i> -value	t	B	logFC	Gene	Rank	%DE
ILMN_1652237	2.17E-05	-4.7872593	2.325104	-0.84032499	CBR3	5328/47229	88.7

Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma tumor tissue, we discovered differential expression of carbonyl reductase 3, encoded by CBR3 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 1**). The expression of CBR3 changed more than 88% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 47,229 transcripts ("Rank"). Note the negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CBR3

1 messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors, demonstrating up-regulation of CBR3 during transformation of
2 the brain from normal brain tissue to glioblastoma.

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4 2. Primary tumors of the brain from humans with brain cancer: glioblastoma.

5 $n=3$ normal brain tissues (human)

6 $n=3$ primary tumors (brain; human; glioblastoma)

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ID	p-value	lfcSE	stat	log2FoldChange	baseMean	Gene	Rank	%DE
874	6.46E-03	0.565	-2.723491	-1.5377012	249.92	CBR3	3379/19678	82.8

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9 Through quantitative comparison of total transcription in normal brain tissues and glioblastoma
10 tumors in a second RNA-sequencing dataset from independent investigators and a separate patient cohort,
11 we validated differential expression of CBR3 in glioblastoma in humans (**Chart 2**). The expression of
12 CBR3 here changed more than 80% of the human brain and brain tumor transcriptome when considering
13 all transcripts whose expression was measured - in this case, 19,678 transcripts (“Rank”). Note the
14 negative fold-change indicating increased quantity of CBR3 messenger RNA in glioblastoma tumors,
15 demonstrating up-regulation of CBR3 during transformation of the brain from normal brain tissue to
16 glioblastoma.

17 Thus, CBR3 is a gene whose differential expression defines the transcriptional landscape of the
18 glioblastoma subtype in humans.

19 CBR3 transcriptional co-regulation.

20 Finally, we utilized a separate systems methodology that utilizes whole transcriptome data to
21 provide insight into molecular function of a gene product by evaluating the transcriptional network within
22 which it operates through identification of co-regulated gene partners.

27 In the transformed brain, CBR3 was transcriptionally co-regulated with PSMB8, PSME2, CASP4,
28 PSMB9, PPIB, TIMP1, CLIC1 and IL10RB.

1 Thus, blind comparative transcriptome analysis of glioblastomas revealed differential expression of
2 CBR3 as among the most significant transcriptional features of glioblastoma tumors; systems level query
3 into CBR3 molecular function across multiple tissues at the transcriptome level revealed its co-regulation
4 with PSMB8, PSME2, CASP4, PSMB9, PPIB, TIMP1, CLIC1 and IL10RB.

4 **Discussion**

5 We found by mining published and public microarray and RNA-sequencing data (5, 6) that the
6 carbonyl reductase 3, CBR3, was among the genes most differentially expressed in the
7 primary tumors of patients with glioblastoma; CBR3 was expressed at significantly higher levels in
8 glioblastoma tumors as compared to the brain. CBR3 is a target of interest for rationally designed medical
9 treatment of glioblastoma, a difficult to treat adult solid tumor.
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